

MODELLING THE GEOMETRIC VARIABILITY OF 3D WOVEN GLASS FIBRE FABRIC AND ITS EFFECTS ON PERMEABILITY

X. Zhao^{1,2}, A.C.Long¹, E. Sitnikova¹, S. Li¹

¹ Polymer Composites Research Group, Faculty of Engineering, University of Nottingham, University Park, Nottingham, NG7 2RD, U.K

²AVIC Commercial Aircraft Engine, Co. Ltd. (ACAE),
Shanghai, 201108, China

Email: xiantao.zhao@hotmail.com or emxxz@nottingham.ac.uk

Keywords: X-Ray micro-CT, 3D woven, Geometry variability, Permeability prediction

ABSTRACT

A 3D woven ply to ply angle interlock glass fabric was characterized with X-ray micro-CT technology. The internal geometry was regenerated from image processing and segmentation. Geometry variability can be characterized by analysing yarn paths and cross sections within the sample. Three cases study models with different internal variability were generated with TexGen to investigate preliminarily the influence of geometric variability on corresponding permeability prediction. This research presented herein forms the basis for future investigation in permeability variability related with fabric geometry variability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Generally, fabrics are fabricated by weaving fibre yarns with different internal structures. From the perspective of the macro scale, the reinforcement can be seen as composed of periodic repeated 'unit cells'. The mechanical or manufacturing simulation process can be conducted on this meso-scale 'unit cell' to represent the macro scale component.

However, recent studies show that variability introduced at different stages can affect the performance or simulation process [1-3]. Endruweit and Long [1, 2] investigated the influence of fibre angle variations on the permeability of bi-directional non-crimp glass fibre textile fabrics. By assigning normally distributed fibre angles and statistical deviations to the geometric models, it is found that the mean mould filling time increases with increasing fibre angle variability. Desplentere et al. [4] describes the stochastic flow modelling process considering the variability of permeability induced by fabric geometry variability, variation of resin viscosity and the correlation of permeability distribution at the macro scale. Skordos et al. [3] investigated the influence of geometric variability in pre-impregnated carbon/epoxy satin weave textile on its forming process. It is found that the variability in tow orientations is significant. Auto correlated stochastic variables are employed to model the woven textile over the plane. Results show that coefficients of wrinkling strain variations in the processed components can be as high as 10-20%. Mehrez et al. [5, 6] investigated stochastic macro scale material properties from a finite number of experimental tests. An experimental database of Young's modulus from twenty-one specimens was constructed. A probabilistic approach was applied to associate the variability of these measurements with the random field model. Zhang et al. [7, 8] proposed a methodology to predict the realistic permeability field and fluctuation by statistically describing the non-woven random micro structure. The statistical characteristics of the fabric internal structure were incorporated into a permeability prediction process based on Darcy's law. A comparison between numerical prediction and radial injection experiments validated its effectiveness. Besides, the random permeability was employed as input on the simulation of the mould filling process to qualifying uncertainty of the resin flow front progression. It was found that the stochastic randomness with process modelling should be considered together with the deterministic solutions.

With the application of advanced material characterization techniques, the variability in the internal geometry of fabric can be better quantified. In Desplentere et al. [9] research, X-ray micro-CT characterization methodology of 3D textiles was compared with the traditional optical microscopy method. With no statistically significant measurement difference between the two methods, it was demonstrated that the X-ray micro-CT can be used reliably to acquire the internal geometry of fabrics. Vanaerschot et al. [10-12] applied the reference period collation method [13] to analyse the stochastic characteristics of nested laminates. Virtual specimens were generated in the WiseTex software possessing the same statistical information from experiments. It was found that the simulated cross-correlated random fields of tow position possess the same standard deviation and correlation lengths as experiments. Regarding with the meso-scale unit cell based permeability modelling [14] process, Wong [15, 16] studied the effects of textile variability at mesoscale on its evaluated permeability variation. Tow paths at cross-overs were randomly generated based on a given normal distribution within the TexGen software. It was observed that the predicted permeability variation increased with the increasing tow position variability. The sensitivity of permeability prediction to the geometrical variations and model refinement was investigated by Zeng et al. [17]. Better quantitative agreement with experimental results can be obtained from highly accurate local yarn geometries.

From all the above research, it can be concluded that geometric variability inherent within real fibrous reinforcements affects the results of numerical simulations of processing and performance. Specifically, the stochastic variations from the ‘average’ unit cell model should be considered in the process of predicting permeability. As a preliminary research on the internal variability of a 3D woven angle-interlock glass fibre fabric in this paper, X-ray micro-CT is applied to acquire three-dimensional (3-D) images of a moulded sample. An image processing methodology is developed to characterize fibre yarn geometry such as yarn paths and cross sections from analysing these stacked 3-D image slices. Case studies on the influence of geometry variability on the permeability prediction based on Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) are conducted with three models generated with TexGen.

2 MATERIAL PREPARATION

2.1 Material and Sample Preparation

The material addressed in this paper is a glass fibre 3D woven angle-interlock fabric supplied by SINOMA. The schematic architecture is as shown in Figure. 1.

Figure 1: Schematic weaving geometry of angle-interlock 3D woven textile

A 300mm by 300mm panel was manufactured with Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). Dry fabric was placed into the mould cavity with a thickness of 3.7mm, resulting in a fibre volume fraction of the moulded panel of around 61%. To obtain a high scanned resolution, the specimen for X-Ray micro-CT is prepared with dimensions of 22.7mm by 12.8mm by 3.7mm in warp, weft and through thickness directions respectively.

2.2 Image Acquisition by micro-CT

The X-ray micro-CT was conducted on the Phoenix V|TOME|X M 240 (GE Sensing & Inspection Technologies GmbH). The images were collected using X-rays of energy 80kV and with a current of

95 μ A. The sample was scanned in two parts, with a rotation step by 0.2°, giving 1800 radiograph images over a period of 60mins in each part. Detector exposure for each image is 500ms. Datas Acquisition and Reconstruction Software were used to tile these two-dimensional slices into sample size. The entire sample data consists of 2718 by 1774 by 570 in three directions respectively. With this scanning method, a pixel resolution of 8 μ m can be obtained.

3 IMAGE ANALYSIS

The micro-CT data consists of detailed internal geometric information by stacking a number of image slices in warp, weft and through-thickness directions. Although 3D reconstruction of the whole specimen is possible, it is still difficult to determine internal tow paths directly from this data. As a result, the weave structure such as tow path, tow shape and cross sections are obtained by an image segmentation method stated below.

3.1 Overview of Internal Structure

There are 6 layers of warp yarns and 6 layers of weft yarns in the through thickness direction, with overlapping warp yarns on the top surface but ‘suspended’ interval weft yarns at the bottom surface (Fig. 2). Due to the contact with the mould inner surface, the surface warp yarns experience a higher compression than internal ones. Thus, warp yarns in this sample can be grouped in two categories: surface warps and internal warps.

The weft yarns are highly stacked in ‘column’ style from weft view as shown in Fig. 2. The ‘columned’ weft yarns are bearing a ‘flattened’ effect which makes their cross sections deviate from an ideal elliptical shape. Accordingly, warp yarns are also influenced by this ‘flattened’ effect at cross-overs, but ‘loosened’ across gaps between weft yarns. This ‘loosened’ effect inevitably affects the warp yarn cross section shape greatly. The bottom weft yarns experience an ‘elongation’ effect caused by missing bottom bounding warp yarns as well as contact with the mould surface. Therefore, weft yarns in this sample can be separated in two categories: internal weft and bottom weft.

Figure 2: Internal structure observation

3.2 Image Processing

The internal geometry information such as fibre yarn path, yarn cross section shape, as well as yarn volume occupied within the sample are all stored within the micro-CT data set as a group of pixels with various brightness and grey scale. Accordingly, fibre yarn paths and shape can be described by distinguishing the boundaries between different yarns and the matrix. A series of adjacent slices are stacked into one image slice to better distinguish between warp and weft yarns, just as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Image process with local projection and sharpening

Yarn cross section shape selection tools within the image processing software (ImageJ) range from rounded rectangular to ellipses. The yarn cross sections can be characterized by fitting ellipse. Thus, the cross sectional area, the lengths of major and minor axis of these transformed ellipses, the coordinates of its centroid, as well as the orientation of its axis system can be obtained through this image recognition procedure.

Theoretically, the exact internal weave structure can be regenerated from processing all these slices along the yarn path (the interval between neighboring slices equals the pixel resolution of $8\mu\text{m}$ in this study). However, model generation should not ‘copy’ the real fabric structure, but should contain the ‘critical’ information. Specifically speaking, the ‘critical’ information related to the internal structure in this study is weft yarn cross section centroids at the crossover locations, as not only weft yarn path and spacing can be described by yarn cross section centroids, but also warp yarn information such as yarn height can be acquired indirectly. As there are five weft yarns contained in this sample, the middle one is selected as the reference weft yarn; image slices are stacked along this yarn. The stacking distance is exactly the specific warp width; this can be determined by the sudden change of warp yarn weave style when crossing over the reference weft yarn. The obtained image is a homogenization of all the stacked slices based on average pixel intensity. In this way, the stacked image can be considered as located at the median slice (within all stacked slices), which also represents the crossover location. To make it clear, the stacking schematic is presented in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Slices stacking schematic

(a) View from through-thickness direction; (b) View from warp and weft direction respectively;

(c) Weft cross section recognition in one stacked image

12 stacked images can be obtained (wt1~wt12) by grouping all the slices manually. Note that the first and last stacked image wt1 and wt12 are omitted in the following variability analysis, as their ‘median slice’ location is not at crossovers due to ‘truncation effect’ at the specimen edge (see Fig. 4 (a)). For each stacked image, information including weft yarn cross section shape and area, and centroids (which represent yarn loci) can be retrieved from weft yarn cross sections. All these data are stored in the form of $T_{ijk}(x_{ijk}, y_{ijk}, z_{ijk}), A_{ijk}(w_{ijk}, h_{ijk})$, of which:

T_{ijk} refers to the specific weft yarn cross section;

i represents the specific stacked image number, ranging from 1 to 12;
 j represents layer number, ranging from 1 to 6;
 k represents ‘column’ number, or crossover number along the warp direction, ranging from 1 to 5;
 x y z represents yarn cross section centroid coordinates in warp, weft and through thickness direction respectively, note that actually, y is the median slice location in the weft direction, which is determined by the applied slice-stacking arrangement in this research;
 A represents the specific weft yarn cross section area;
 w h represent the transformed elliptical major and minor lengths;

From the above image processing and measurements, a series of data can be acquired to characterize the internal woven structure of this angle-interlock 3D woven glass fibre fabric. This will be presented in the following section.

4. GEOMETRY VARIABILITY STUDY

With the image processing methodology described in section 3.2, a data set with 300 weft yarn cross sections (10 stacked images, 30 weft cross sections on each image) can be obtained.

4.1 Weft Yarn Path Deviation

The cross section centroids are positioned as shown in Fig. 5. Following the notation rules described in section 3.2, the axis title x z labeled in Fig. 5 represent distance from top left corner on each stacked image (wt2~wt11) in warp direction and through thickness direction respectively (assuming a plane-coordinate system is set on each stacked image with the top left corner as the origin of coordinates). Fig. 5(a) shows the positions of weft cross section centroids with detailed information in ‘Column 1’; (b) gives an overview of all obtained weft yarn cross section centroid positions. An obvious regular ‘shear’ deformation in through-thickness direction is revealed from these inclined weft columns. On each layer, each weft yarn is represented by 10 centroids, of which a ‘shift’ phenomenon can be observed. This indicates that yarn path is not in idealized ‘straight’ form, but presents a deviation in the warp direction (x direction). Besides, it is rational to hypothesize a linear fitting to illustrate this shear deformation. Multi linear regression analysis is applied on each column data. Figure 5 (b) presents the linear fitting results for each column. Note that centroids data from layer 6 is not included in this fitting process as it shows a large deviation from the perceived linear fitting derived from the other 5 layers.

Figure 5: Weft yarn deviation

(a) Detailed weft yarn cross section centroids re-position in ‘Column 1’; (b) Overall view of weft yarn cross section re-position

4.2 Weft Spacing Variability

The ‘shifting’ effect of weft yarn cross section centroids in the warp (x) direction analyzed in last section will inevitably impose a deviation on weft spacing. Figure 6 shows the weft spacing in different layers along the weft direction (axis y). The notation ‘ ts_i ’ is used to refer to the four weft spacing obtained in each stacked image. The specific weft spacing deviations exhibit a stochastic characteristic, yet a common deviation from the nominal weft spacing (3.85mm displayed as the red dashed line) provided by the supplier can be found. Besides, a decreasing trend can be found among the four acquired weft spacing in each layer, generally with the maximum value on ts_1 and the minimum value on ts_4 . This may be caused by the instability of the weaving process during dry fabric manufacture; moreover, an obvious ‘complementary’ effect can be revealed between the adjacent two weft spacing.

Figure 6: Weft spacing variability

4.3 Warp Yarn Geometry Determination

Another variability that cannot be overlooked is related with warp yarn path and cross section. It can be clearly observed in figure 3 that the warp height along warp path can be separated into two categories: warp height at crossovers and between weft yarns. Note that the two warp cross sections (with different warp height) at the two specified locations should be connected smoothly when generating models. In this paper, the warp height is characterized with the arithmetic computation illustrated in Fig. 7, of which:

T_j represents weft centroids z coordinate;

h_j represents weft yarn height obtained from ellipse fitting illustrated in above sections;

- H represents warp height at crossover location;
- H' represents the maximum warp height in the middle of weft spacing;
- θ : represents the angle between warp path and x axis;

Figure 7: Warp height determination

The method illustrated in Fig. 7 is an indirect way to characterize warp height at critical locations along warp loci. This method is credible in that all the inputs for this computation are obtained directly from processing the stacked micro-CT images in section 3.2. Note that the average weft spacing is employed here in this preliminary study to acquire the varied ‘maximum’ warp height (the maximum warp height is obtained when the two neighboring warp yarns are closely adjacent to each other in through thickness direction). Similarly, in this paper the surface and internal warp width is acquired as an averaged value from fitting the warp cross sections at crossovers.

4.4 Summarized Internal Geometry

From all the above image analysis, the geometry parameters for this 3D woven ply-to-ply angle inter-lock glass fibre fabric (with average value, standard deviation) are presented in Table.1.

		Surface warp	Internal warp	Internal weft	Bottom weft
Width	[mm]	2.30±0.091	1.24±0.003	2.790±0.185	3.387±0.103
Height	[mm]	0.330±0.014	0.249±0.023	0.350±0.026	0.315±0.040
Spacing	[mm]	2.46±0.094	1.24±0.003	3.993±0.176	3.993±0.176

Table 1: Internal geometry summary

5. CASE STUDIES OF INFLUENCE OF GEOMETRY VARIABILITY ON PERMEABILITY PREDICTION

5.1 Unit Cell Generation

TexGen is used to generate the specific unit cell model based on the geometry analysis illustrated in section 4. By modelling the yarn path and interpolating various yarn cross sections along yarn paths, the required internal geometry can be reconstructed. Note that the aim of this research is to investigate the influence of geometry variability on the predicted permeability based on unit cell conception. According to the internal geometry variability analysis in the last section, ‘unit cell’ here should contain both the averaged geometric information and the variation information (stochastic deviations from the averaged geometry parameters). In this way, the real fabric can be better represented. This

can be realized by an automatic generation method of a series of ‘unit cell’s in accordance with the genuine geometrical variability. Bearing this in mind, as an initial study, three models are generated and applied in this paper to see their effects on the predicted permeability, as shown in Fig. 8. The idealised unit cell model is generated based on the averaged geometry parameters listed in Table. 1; modification 1 is obtained by shearing the weft yarn ‘column’ according to the geometry analysis (ϕ) in section 4. Modification 2 is acquired by interpolating the various yarn cross section (the middle cross section obtained from section 4.3) in the middle of the warp yarn.

Figure 8 Unit cell representations

(a) Idealised model; (b) Feature description for modification 1 (sheared weft yarns) (c) Feature description for modification 2 (warp height varied in the middle of warp yarn)

Besides, it should be mentioned that the three case study models cannot be employed as verification models as the surface yarn deviation (overlapped warp yarn on top surface, suspended weft yarns on bottom surface) is not considered in this initial study. Therefore, at present the permeability prediction results obtained in the following section cannot be applied as validation results against experimental permeability values.

5.2 Flow Modelling

Steady state, laminar flow is applied across the flow domain; air is used as the flow media as it can be considered as an incompressible fluid at low speed. Note that in this paper the yarns are modelled as impermeable with yarn surface simulated as no-slip walls [18]. The Navier-Stokes equation was solved within the gaps between fibre yarns. Translational periodicity is assigned in all three directions. The flow is driven by applying a constant pressure gradient across the flow domain. In this study, conformal mesh with around 120,000 elements is generated within the flow domain. This flow modelling process is completed with the commercial CFD software Ansys CFX 14.0. The saturated permeability in warp, weft and through thickness direction can be calculated from Darcy’s law with the obtained flow rate in each specific direction.

5.3 Results and Discussion

Fig. 9 presents the comparison of predicted permeability from the three case study models in warp, weft and through thickness direction respectively.

Figure 9: Comparison of predicted permeabilities

It can be found that the influence of geometry modification on the simulation results can be significant. Generally the two modifications tend to reduce the predicted permeability, with an exception that the sheared modification displays a similar predicted value in the warp direction compared with the idealised model. Specifically, the modification with interpolated warp cross section decreases the predicted results most: the permeability in the weft direction predicted from the idealised model is almost twice the value predicted from modification model 2.

With the yarns simulated as impermeable solid, the flow process through these models is controlled by the flow within the gaps between yarns. Thus, permeability predicted in the weft direction in all the three models shows the maximum value as more gaps exist as flow channels in this direction. With the interpolated increased warp cross sections in modification 2, the yarn volume fraction can reach as high as 79.8%, which accordingly will almost eliminate the flow channels, resulting in the minimum predicted results in modification 2 among all three models. However, although the modified model 1 with sheared weft yarns possesses the same yarn volume fraction (67.4%) as the idealised model, the flow channels are still changed with the modified warp path from the sheared deformation, as shown in Fig. 10. In particular, it seems the flow is more affected by the ‘narrowed’ flow channels between warp yarns.

Figure 10: Changed flow channels with modified model 1

The case studies discussed above indicate that the flow simulation output is highly sensitive to geometry variability such as yarn path and cross sections. Note that the varied models generated in this paper are only used as representations of the effects of geometry variability on permeability prediction. The internal geometry of the real fabric will present a much more complicated geometry variability across the whole material, as analysed in section 4. This geometric characteristic should be taken into account when dealing with permeability prediction based on unit cell. In our ongoing research, models with stochastic geometric variability will be generated based on the stochastic spatial information obtained from material characterization. Flow modelling based on these varied models will be conducted to reveal its impact.

6. CONCLUSION

From X-ray micro-CT characterization of this 3D woven angle interlock ply to ply glass fabric, the internal geometry is characterized by image processing. The geometry variability is investigated by analyzing yarn paths and cross sections along yarn loci. As a preliminary study on the influence of geometry variability on the predicted permeability results, three case studies with two modified models are conducted. The results indicate that permeability prediction is highly sensitive to the model geometry deviation. A systematic study of permeability prediction variability induced by geometry variability based on the material characterization is being conducted in our ongoing research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support from AVIC Commercial Aircraft Engine, Co. Ltd. (ACAE), China, through Grant No. RGS106619 is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] Endruweit, A., A.C. Long, F. Robitaille, and C.D. Rudd, *Influence of stochastic fibre angle variations on the permeability of bi-directional textile fabrics*. Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing, 2006. **37**(1): p. 122-132.
- [2] Endruweit, A. and A.C. Long, *Influence of stochastic variations in the fibre spacing on the permeability of bi-directional textile fabrics*. Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing, 2006. **37**(5): p. 679-694.
- [3] Skordos, A.A. and M.P.F. Sutcliffe, *Stochastic simulation of woven composites forming*. Composites Science and Technology, 2008. **68**(1): p. 283-296.
- [4] Desplentere, F., I. Verpoest, and S. Lomov, *Stochastic Flow Modeling for Resin Transfer Moulding*. AIP Conference Proceedings, 2009. **1152**(1): p. 284-292.
- [5] Mehrez, L., D. Moens, and D. Vandepitte, *Stochastic identification of composite material properties from limited experimental databases, part I: Experimental database construction*. Mechanical systems and signal processing, 2012. **27**: p. 471-483.
- [6] Mehrez, L., A. Doostan, D. Moens, and D. Vandepitte, *Stochastic identification of composite material properties from limited experimental databases, Part II: Uncertainty modelling*. Mechanical systems and signal processing, 2012. **27**: p. 484-498.
- [7] Zhang, F., B. Cosson, S. Comas-Cardona, and C. Binetruy, *Efficient stochastic simulation approach for RTM process with random fibrous permeability*. Composites Science and Technology, 2011. **71**(12): p. 1478-1485.
- [8] Zhang, F., S. Comas-Cardona, and C. Binetruy, *Statistical modeling of in-plane permeability of non-woven random fibrous reinforcement*. Composites Science and Technology, 2012. **72**(12): p. 1368-1379.
- [9] Desplentere, F., S.V. Lomov, D.L. Woerdeman, I. Verpoest, M. Wevers, and A. Bogdanovich, *Micro-CT characterization of variability in 3D textile architecture*. Composites Science and Technology, 2005. **65**(13): p. 1920-1930.
- [10] Vanaerscot, A., B.N. Cox, S.V. Lomov, and D. Vandepitte, *Simulation of the cross-correlated positions of in-plane tow centroids in textile composites based on experimental data*. Composite Structures, 2014. **116**: p. 75-83.
- [11] Vanaerscot, A., B.N. Cox, S.V. Lomov, and D. Vandepitte, *Stochastic framework for quantifying the geometrical variability of laminated textile composites using micro-computed tomography*. Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing, 2013. **44**: p. 122-131.
- [12] Vanaerscot, A., B.N. Cox, S.V. Lomov, and D. Vandepitte, *Stochastic multi-scale modelling of textile composites based on internal geometry variability*. Computers & Structures, 2013. **122**: p. 55-64.

- [13] Bale, H., M. Blacklock, M.R. Begley, D.B. Marshall, B.N. Cox, and R.O. Ritchie, *Characterizing Three - Dimensional Textile Ceramic Composites Using Synchrotron X - Ray Micro - Computed - Tomography*. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2012. **95**(1): p. 392-402.
- [14] Verleye, B., S.V. Lomov, A. Long, I. Verpoest, and D. Roose, *Permeability prediction for the meso-macro coupling in the simulation of the impregnation stage of Resin Transfer Moulding*. Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing, 2010. **41**(1): p. 29-35.
- [15] Wong, C.C., *Modelling the effects of textile preform architecture on permeability*, 2006, University of Nottingham.
- [16] Wong, C.C. and A.C. Long, *Modelling variation of textile fabric permeability at mesoscopic scale*. Plastics, Rubber and Composites, 2006. **35**(3): p. 101-111.
- [17] Zeng, X., L.P. Brown, A. Endruweit, M. Matveev, and A.C. Long, *Geometrical modelling of 3D woven reinforcements for polymer composites: Prediction of fabric permeability and composite mechanical properties*. Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing, 2014. **56**(0): p. 150-160.
- [18] Zeng, X., A. Endruweit, L.P. Brown, and A.C. Long, *Numerical prediction of in-plane permeability for multilayer woven fabrics with manufacture-induced deformation*. Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing, 2015.